

Information Theoretic-Based Optimal Sensor Placement for Virtual Sensing using Augmented Kalman Filtering

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Abstract

An optimal sensor placement (OSP) framework for virtual sensing using the augmented Kalman Filter (AKF) technique is presented based on information and utility theory. The framework is applicable to input and response reconstruction when output-only vibration measurements are available. Using information theory, a utility function is built to quantify the expected information gained from the data for reducing the uncertainty of unmeasured quantities of interest (QoI). Taking into account the AKF equations and exploiting the Gaussian nature of the response QoI arising from linear dynamic systems, useful and informative analytical expressions are derived for the utility function. Subsequently, the utility function is extended to make the OSP design robust to uncertainties in the structural model and modeling error parameters, resulting in a multidimensional integral of the expected information gain over all possible values of the uncertain parameters, weighted by their assigned probability distributions. The proposed OSP framework maximizes this utility function through heuristic sequential sensor placement (SSP) strategies (forward and backward SSP) and genetic algorithms (GA) to optimize the type and location of sensors. A new modified SSP strategy is proposed that exploits the computational efficiency of the less accurate forward SSP algorithm and the accuracy of the computationally expensive backward SSP algorithm. A thorough study of the effect of measurements, modelling, input, and prediction uncertainties on the selection of the optimal sensor configuration is presented using a Finite Element (FE) model of a plate loaded by a single concentrated input force, highlighting the importance of accounting for robustness to errors and other uncertainties.

Keywords: Kalman filtering; virtual sensing; response reconstruction; information gain; Kullback-Leibler divergence; utility theory

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

AKF augmented Kalman filtering

BSSP backward sequential sensor placement

DOF degrees of freedom

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FE Finite Element
 FSSP forward sequential sensor placement
 GA genetic algorithm
 KF Kalman filter
 KL-div Kullback-Leibler divergence
 M-BSSP modified backward sequential sensor placement
 OSP optimal sensor placement
 QoI quantity of interest
 SSP sequential sensor placement
 TTS time to solution

Symbols

α level of the load model error
 β parameter quantifying the uncertainty in s
 γ parameter quantifying the uncertainty in σ_e and σ_ε
 Ψ observation matrix
 σ_e level of model error in R
 σ_x level of process noise
 Σ_z steady-state error covariance matrix
 σ_ε level of prediction error
 σ_{wn}^2 variance of the discrete white noise excitation
 $\underline{\varepsilon}$ prediction error
 \underline{v} measurement error
 $\underline{\delta}$ sensor configuration vector
 $\underline{\omega}$ process noise vector
 $\underline{\varphi}$ model parameters
 $\underline{\xi}$ vector of modal coordinates
 \underline{u} load vector
 \underline{x} state vector

\underline{y}	vector of response time history data
\underline{z}	vector of predicted responses
A, B, G, J	state-space matrices
D	the available data
$H_{z D}$	posterior information entropy
H_z	prior information entropy
k	time index
m	number of contributing modes
n	number of model degrees of freedom
N_{all}	number of all possible sensor positions
N_{start}	number of initial possible sensor positions
n_u	number of point loads
n_z	number of response locations
P_k	Kalman filter error covariance matrix
Q	process noise covariance matrix
Q_a	Augmented process noise covariance matrix
Q_u	covariance of the load intensity
Q_x	covariance of the state vector
Q_y	square of the intensity of the observed QoI
Q_z	square of the intensity of the predicted QoI
R	observation error covariance matrix
R_ε	prediction error covariance matrix
S	load model error covariance matrix
s	level of measurement error in R
t	time
U	expected utility function
N_0	number of sensors

1. Introduction

In the context of structural identification, the calculation of dynamical responses is required for system identification, damage detection, reliability analysis, and fatigue monitoring. Although physical sensors serve to provide such information, their usage naturally visits budget constraints, as well as practical considerations like inaccessibility of positions and infeasibility of obtaining direct measurements. Consequently, the reconstruction of unknown quantities from a limited number of physical sensors, also referred to as "virtual sensing", has attracted extensive attention due to its pivotal role in monitoring performance/safety-related indices, e.g., accelerations, displacements, inter-story drifts, strains, and stresses. However, the success of virtual sensing in structural dynamics heavily depends on proper placement of a limited number of sensors, which is the subject of the present work.

Modal expansion and filtering techniques are conventional virtual sensing tools. Modal expansion has been introduced in the past for stress [1] and strain [2–4] reconstruction from limited sets of data. Recently, Bayesian techniques for response reconstruction and virtual sensing based on modal expansion have also been developed to account for model uncertainties and uncertainties in measurements and predictions [5, 6]. Filtering techniques have also been developed for reconstruction the external forces [7–9] using limited number of vibration measurements such as acceleration and/or strain response time histories. They have also been extended to combined input-state estimation and response reconstruction [10, 11] as well as input-state-parameter estimation [12, 13]. In particular, they have been used for virtual sensing of strains [14] and stresses [15] using limited number of vibration measurements.

Although the modal expansion technique can reconstruct unobserved history responses, it cannot calculate external loadings applied to the structure. Additionally, the modal expansion is not flexible enough for fusing different types of physical sensors as it only applies to estimating dynamical responses, e.g., strains, displacements, and accelerations, from the same kind of sensors. In contrast, filtering techniques, including Minimum-Variance Unbiased filters [10] and Bayesian filtering methods [16, 17], can handle both input reconstruction and multi-type sensor fusion.

Virtual sensing of strain/stress responses is necessary for fatigue damage identification. Papadimitriou et al. [18, 19] were the first to combine output-only vibration measurements, FE models, and virtual sensing tools with stochastic and deterministic fatigue theories for characterizing fatigue damage accumulation in the entire body of metallic structures. Such predictions are based on the actual operating conditions of structures and thus provide realistic fatigue estimates consistent with existing fatigue theories.

In recent years, modal expansion and filtering techniques were applied for strain/stress virtual sensing for numerous structures using a limited number of displacement/strain/acceleration sensors, including offshore monopile wind turbines [20, 21], wind turbine towers [22, 23], wind turbine towers with jacket substructures [24], truss structures [25], underwater structures [26] and mechanical components [27, 28]. In addition, they have been promoted for fatigue estimation based on strain/stress estimation for a number of structures, including offshore wind turbines [29], roller coaster [30], mechanical components of industrial structures [31–33] and railway bridges [34]. Substructure decoupling of linear and nonlinear models of structures has been integrated into fatigue monitoring methods, which uses filtering techniques for identifying the forces at the interface between the analyzed linear substructure (or component) and the rest of the structure [35–38].

Optimal sensor placement techniques for structural dynamics applications have been proposed to extract the most informative data that will increase the accuracy of the estimates from a given number of sensors. A recent article [39] reviews the subject, summarizing methods and

optimization algorithms for optimizing the location of sensors in structural dynamics applications. However, a limited number of OSP studies exist for virtual sensing based on output-only vibration measurements.

Based on filtering techniques introduced for the case of unknown loads, a number of OSP methods have been developed recently for state estimation and response reconstruction [28, 40, 41], as well as for load estimation [42, 43]. The methods are based on minimizing a scalar measure of the steady-state reconstruction error covariance of the response and/or input with respect to the location of sensors. In most of the approaches, the scalar measure is chosen to be the trace of the reconstruction error covariance matrix. The use of a scalar measure (usually the trace) of the steady-state covariance of the reconstruction error is borrowed from optimal sensor placement strategies proposed in structural dynamics applications for response reconstruction based on Kalman-type filter methods subjected to known loads [44–46]. The size of the reduction of the measure as a function of the number of sensors is used to select a reasonable number of sensors. More specifically, in [47] a multi-type OSP strategy is proposed based on Gillijns and De Moor filtering technique [48], demonstrating the OSP to be independent of the type and time evolution of the external excitation(s). The forward sequential sensor placement (FSSP) technique [49] was used as a heuristic algorithm to carry out the optimization problem in which acceleration and strain sensors were added sequentially at their optimal location that maximizes the estimation error of the reconstructed responses. In a very similar approach, Peng et al. [41] proposed the backward sequential placement (BSSP) algorithm [49], instead of the FSSP algorithm, to optimize the location of acceleration and strain sensors.

Focusing on optimal sensor placement for multiple load estimation, a method is proposed in [43] based on the condition number of a system observability metric using AKF for linear systems [7, 50] and using extended Kalman filter for nonlinear system [51]. Recognising that observability offers only the minimum requirements for a stable estimation, two alternative metrics for best load identification are proposed in [42], based on steady-state error covariance of the load estimation and sensor bandwidth through the transfer function between real and estimated inputs. The metric in the first method involves the trace of the steady-state error covariance of the load estimation. Satisfying conditions of observability and invertability, Maes et al. [52] proposed an optimal sensor layout for load estimation which leads to a minimum set of position and acceleration sensors equal to the number of loads to be identified.

Information theoretic-based methods have also been used in structural dynamics to optimize the sensor configuration.

In these methods a measure of the information gained from the sensor data, such as information entropy [53–55], mutual information [56, 57], joint entropy [58], expected Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL-div) [59–61] and utility theory [62, 63] computed from a Bayesian formulation is optimized with respect to the sensor locations. An OSP technique for response predictions based on Bayesian formulation and consistent with information theory has been developed in [64] in the case of known input.

OSP techniques based on information-theoretic methods for virtual sensing under unknown input has also been proposed based on either the kriging technique [65] or modal expansion technique [66, 67], while limited studies exist for filtering techniques [68, 69] for input and response reconstruction.

The outcome of OSP depends on the objectives set in the optimization function, so the alteration of optimization objectives can change the position of sensors. Although the literature is rich in terms of optimal sensor placement for modal identification and parameter estimation, there exist gaps in developing sensor placement strategies, tailored for both response and input reconstruc-

tion. This paper intends to fill this gap by proposing a new information theoretic-based approach, which benefits from the stationary solutions of the AKF and heuristic optimization algorithms.

In this work, considering the availability of output-only vibration measurements, a novel OSP framework is presented for accurate virtual sensing (response and/or load reconstruction) in linear systems based on the AKF technique and information theory. The information gained by a sensor configuration is measured by the KL-div [70] between the posterior and prior probability distribution of the response QoI to be virtually sensed or reconstructed at each time step, by combining available AKF techniques and sensor data. This is obtained using the Lindley's utility function [71, 72] quantifying the average information in the data over all possible measurements generated by the prediction error model. For more than one reconstructed QoI, the KL-div is averaged over all possible virtually sensed QoI. For linear models of systems, exact analytical expressions are developed for the utility function in terms of the variance of the responses of the virtually sensed QoI. The utility measure is extended to include uncertainties in the model parameters, as well as in the modelling, prediction and measurement errors, which during the experimental design phase are subjectively assigned in the modeling and filtering process. The optimal sensor configuration is finally obtained by maximizing the expected information gain over all possible values of the uncertain parameters. The resulting multidimensional integral are computed using sparse grid or Monte Carlo techniques. Heuristic algorithms and a GA are introduced to carry out the discrete optimization problem. The high computational burden associated with BSSP and the lack of sufficient accuracy of the FSSP are discussed, and remedies are proposed to attain an accurate and computationally efficient algorithm.

This study is organized as follows: In Section 2, the AKF technique is outlined for characterizing the uncertainty in the prediction of input and response QoI. In Section 3, the optimal sensor placement methodology is presented based on utility and information theory. An application on a square plate structure is used in Section 4 to demonstrate the capabilities and effectiveness of the OSP methodology for reliable virtual sensing. Conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. Bayesian Virtual Sensing Using Augmented Kalman Filter

Consider a structural model used to predict the temporal variability of the response $\underline{z}(t; \underline{\varphi}) \in R^{n_z}$ (e.g., accelerations, displacements, strain or stresses) at n_z locations given the values of a structural model parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$ (e.g., stiffness, mass and damping related parameters) and the excitation vector $\underline{u}(t) \in R^{n_u}$. Let $D = \{\underline{y}(t) \in R^{N_0}\}$ be the vector of response time history data collected by placing N_0 sensors on the structure. These data depend on the sensor configuration vector $\underline{\delta} \in R^{N_0}$ indicating the location and measurement direction of sensors. The data may consist of acceleration, displacement, and strain measurements.

In what follows, a linear FE model of the structure is assumed with n degrees of freedom (DOF). The governing equations of motion are developed either in the physical space or in the modal space using modal analysis and keeping up to m contributing modes.

2.1. State-Space Formulation

The governing equations of motion of the structure are formulated in state-space form by defining the state vector $\underline{x}(t) \in R^n$ of the displacement and velocity vector or, for the case of modal analysis, the state vector is defined as $\underline{x}(t) = (\underline{\xi}(t), \dot{\underline{\xi}}(t))^T$, with respect to the modal coordinate vector $\underline{\xi}(t) \in R^m$ and its first derivative. Converting the continuous state space equation into the discrete state space using the notation $\underline{x}_k = \underline{x}(k\Delta t)$, where k is the time index and Δt is the

discretization time interval, the discrete state-space system becomes

$$\underline{x}_{k+1} = A\underline{x}_k + B\underline{u}_k + \underline{w}_k \quad (1)$$

where A and B are the system matrices and \underline{w}_k the process noise assumed to be zero-mean Gaussian, i.e. $\underline{w}_k \sim N(\underline{0}, Q)$ with process noise covariance $Q \in R^{2m \times 2m}$. The observation equation is given by

$$\underline{y}_k = G\underline{x}_k + J\underline{u}_k + \underline{v}_k \quad (2)$$

where the measurement error term follows a zero-mean Gaussian distribution, i.e. $\underline{v}_k \sim N(\underline{0}, R)$, with measurement error covariance $R \in R^{N_0 \times N_0}$. The prediction equation takes a similar form to the observation equation,

$$\underline{z}_k = \tilde{G}\underline{x}_k + \tilde{J}\underline{u}_k + \underline{\varepsilon}_k \quad (3)$$

where the prediction error term also follows a Gaussian distribution, i.e. $\underline{\varepsilon}_k \sim N(\underline{0}, R_\varepsilon)$, with prediction error covariance $R_\varepsilon \in R^{n_z \times n_z}$.

2.2. Review of AKF

In this work, it is assumed that the excitation time histories denoted by $\underline{u}(t)$ are not available. Lourens et al. [7] presented an AKF technique to identify the dynamic forces applied to the structure and also estimate the state of the system.

This is achieved by using a random walk model for the forces [50, 73]

$$\underline{u}_{k+1} = \underline{u}_k + \underline{\eta}_k \quad (4)$$

where $\underline{u}_k \equiv \underline{u}(k\Delta t)$ is the input force at $t_k = k\Delta t$, $\underline{\eta}_k \sim N(\underline{0}, S)$ is a zero-mean Gaussian prediction error with covariance matrix $S \in R^{n_u \times n_u}$. The unknown forces are added in the state vector, and then this augmented vector can be estimated using a standard KF (Kalman Filter). Specifically, introducing the augmented state vector $\underline{x}_k^a = [\underline{x}_k^T, \underline{u}_k^T]^T \in R^{2m+n_u}$ and using (1) and (4), the augmented state-space model and observation equations are formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{x}_{k+1}^a &= A_a \underline{x}_k^a + \underline{\zeta}_k \\ \underline{y}_k &= G_a \underline{x}_k^a + \underline{v}_k \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the augmented state space matrix $A_a \in R^{(2m+n_u) \times (2m+n_u)}$ and observation matrix $G_a \in R^{N_0 \times (2m+n_u)}$ are defined as

$$A_a = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}, \quad G_a = [G \quad J] \quad (6)$$

while the augmented process noise covariance matrix $Q_a \in R^{(2m+n_u) \times (2m+n_u)}$ of the zero-mean Gaussian white noise sequence $\underline{\zeta}_k \sim N(0, Q_a)$ is given as

$$Q_a = \begin{bmatrix} Q & 0 \\ 0 & S \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Note that the system and observation matrices A_a and G_a both depend on the structural parameters collected in $\underline{\varphi}$, but this functional relationship is dropped for notation brevity. The augmented state vector can be estimated through the standard KF, which provides the estimate $\hat{\underline{x}}_{k|k}^a$ and the error covariance matrix $P_{k|k} \in R^{(2m+n_u) \times (2m+n_u)}$ obtained using the following time and

measurement update steps:

Time update:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\underline{x}}_{k|k-1}^a &= A_a \hat{\underline{x}}_{k-1|k-1}^a \\ P_{k|k-1} &= A_a P_{k-1|k-1} A_a^T + Q_a\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

Measurement update:

$$\begin{aligned}L_k &= P_{k|k-1} G_a^T (G_a P_{k|k-1} G_a^T + R)^{-1} \\ \hat{\underline{x}}_{k|k}^a &= \hat{\underline{x}}_{k|k-1}^a + L_k (y_k - G_a \hat{\underline{x}}_{k|k-1}^a) \\ P_{k|k} &= P_{k|k-1} - L_k G_a P_{k|k-1}\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

It should be noted that these equations provide the mean and covariance of the underlying Gaussian distribution. Substituting the first of (9) into the third of (9), the error covariance matrix $P_{k|k}$ also takes the convenient form

$$P_{k|k} = P_{k|k-1} - P_{k|k-1} G_a^T (G_a P_{k|k-1} G_a^T + R)^{-1} G_a P_{k|k-1}\quad (10)$$

Using the augmented formulation, the prediction equation (3) takes the form

$$\underline{z}_k = \Psi \underline{x}_k^a + \underline{\varepsilon}_k\quad (11)$$

where $\Psi = [\tilde{G} \quad \tilde{J}]$ with mean $\hat{\underline{z}}_k = \Psi \hat{\underline{x}}_k^a$ and error covariance matrix $P_{z,k|k} \equiv E[(\underline{z}_k - \hat{\underline{z}}_k)(\underline{z}_k - \hat{\underline{z}}_k)^T]$ given by

$$P_{z,k|k} = \Psi P_{k|k} \Psi^T + R_\varepsilon\quad (12)$$

For practical convenience and without loss of generality, stationarity conditions are next assumed, implying that the covariance matrices R , R_ε and S are independent of the time index k . Moreover, the parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$ is augmented to include the parameters defining the covariance matrices R , R_ε and S . Although it is not explicitly stated in the above formulation, the error covariance matrices $P_{k|k-1}$ and $P_{k|k}$ at the time update and the measurement update steps, respectively, depend on the parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$ and the sensor configuration $\underline{\delta}$. This dependence will be explicitly introduced in the formulation provided in the following section.

2.3. Steady-State Formulation of Prediction Error Covariance Matrices for Time and Measurement Update

In particular, the steady-state solution is obtained by setting $P_{k+1|k} = P_{k|k-1} = P_\infty \equiv P_\infty(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) \in R^{(2m+n_u) \times (2m+n_u)}$, where the last notation is introduced to represent the dependence of P_∞ on the model parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$ and the sensor configuration $\underline{\delta}$. Substituting (10) into the first line equation of (9), the converged steady state error covariance P_∞ at the time update step is then obtained by solving the following discrete-time algebraic Riccati equation:

$$A_a P_\infty A_a^T - P_\infty - A_a P_\infty G_a^T (G_a P_\infty G_a^T + R)^{-1} G_a P_\infty A_a^T + Q_a = 0\quad (13)$$

The steady-state solution for the error covariance matrix at the measurement update step is denoted by $P_{k|k} \equiv \Sigma_{x|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$. Setting $P_{k|k-1} = P_\infty$ and $P_{k|k} = \Sigma_{x|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ in (10), one derives that $\Sigma_{x|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ is given in terms of P_∞ as follows:

$$\Sigma_{x|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = P_\infty - P_\infty G_a^T (G_a P_\infty G_a^T + R)^{-1} G_a P_\infty\quad (14)$$

Finally, the steady-state error covariance matrices $P_{z,k|k-1} \equiv \Sigma_z(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ and $P_{z,k|k} \equiv \Sigma_{z|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ of the predicted QoI \underline{z} at the time update and the measurement update steps, respectively, are derived from (14) to be in the form

$$\Sigma_z(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = \Psi P_\infty(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) \Psi^T + R_\varepsilon \quad (15)$$

$$\Sigma_{z|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = \Psi \Sigma_{x|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) \Psi^T + R_\varepsilon \quad (16)$$

Note that from the structure of the process, observation, and prediction equations, the response prediction vector \underline{z} follows a multivariable normal distribution

$$p(\underline{z}|\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = N(\underline{z}|\hat{\underline{z}}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}), \Sigma(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})) \quad (17)$$

with mean $\hat{\underline{z}}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ given by (11) that depends on the data, and covariance matrix $\Sigma(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ given by (15) for the time update step and by (16) for the measurement update step that does not depend on the data. In particular, the variance of the i -th element $z_i(t; \underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ of the response vector $\underline{z}(t; \underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ is given by the i -th diagonal element of the covariance matrix, which simplify to

$$\Sigma_{z_i}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = \psi_i^T P_\infty(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) \psi_i + R_{\varepsilon_{ii}} \quad (18)$$

$$\Sigma_{z_i|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = \psi_i^T \Sigma_{x|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) \psi_i + R_{\varepsilon_{ii}} \quad (19)$$

for the time update and the measurement update steps, respectively, where ψ_i is the i -th row of the matrix Ψ .

The prior variance $\Sigma_{z_i}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ in (18) and the posterior variance $\Sigma_{z_i|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ in Eq. (19), described in terms of the parameters $\underline{\varphi}$ and the sensor locations $\underline{\delta}$, are the main quantities involved in the next section to solve the optimal sensor location problem for response reconstruction. It is clear that these variances are independent of the measurements/data $\underline{y}(t)$ and depend only on the structural model parameters $\underline{\varphi}$, the process, measurement and prediction error covariances Q_a , R and R_ε .

3. Optimal Sensor Placement Formulation

3.1. Expected Utility Using Information Gain

The design objective is to select the sensor configuration (type, location, and number of sensors) that maximizes the information contained in the data for predicting with the least uncertainty in the output response QoI z_i at desirable DOF or locations i . This is achieved by combining the information theory with utility theory to evaluate the usefulness of a sensor configuration. A measure of the information gained from a sensor configuration $\underline{\delta}$ for estimating a response QoI z_i , given a set of data D and the model parameters $\underline{\varphi}$, is the KL-div [70] between the prior and posterior probability distribution of the output QoI z_i . Following Lindley's work [71], utility theory is used to measure the usefulness of the sensor configuration.

The utility function is selected to be the expected KL-div between the prior and posterior distribution of the output QoI z_i over all possible values of the experimental data. Thus, it represents the information gained from the measured data collected from a sensor configuration for predicting the QoI z_i .

At each time step, the information is gained only in the measurement update step of the KF formulation. By solving the Riccati equation, the stationary prior variance $\Sigma_{z_i}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ can be updated, giving the stationary posterior variance $\Sigma_{z_i|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$. Using the steady-state formulation and recognising that the probability distributions of the estimates at the time and measurement

update steps are Gaussian with the variances of these distribution to be independent of the data, the information gained using the data from $k - 1$ to k time instances is given by [66]

$$U_i(\delta, \underline{\varphi}) = -\Delta H_i(\underline{\delta}) = -[H_{z_i|D}(\delta, \underline{\varphi}) - H_{z_i}(\delta, \underline{\varphi})] \quad (20)$$

where $H_{z_i}(\delta, \underline{\varphi})$ and $H_{z_i|D}(\delta, \underline{\varphi})$ are the information entropies corresponding to the Gaussian distributions with variances given by (18) and (19) at the time update and measurement update steps of the KF formulation. Using the expressions for the information entropy of a Gaussian distribution scalar variable written with respect to the variance of the variable, the expected utility function U_i finally takes the form [66]

$$U_i(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = -\frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{\Sigma_{z_i|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})}{\Sigma_{z_i}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})} \quad (21)$$

Here, $U_i(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})$ represents the expected information gain over all possible values of the data, given the value of the model parameters $\underline{\varphi}$.

For several output QoI included in the vector \underline{z} , the information gain measure can be extended to the weighted average of the information gain for all possible output QoI, given as

$$\bar{U}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_z} w_i U_i(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) \quad (22)$$

with $\sum_{i=1}^{N_z} w_i = 1$, $w_i \geq 0$, where the values of the weight w_i are selected to quantify the importance of the i -th QoI z_i in the design of the sensor configuration. Substituting Eq. (21) into Eq. (22), and extending the utility function to include the uncertainty in the model parameters $\underline{\varphi}$, the expected utility function that accounts for all response entries in the vector \underline{z} takes the form

$$U(\underline{\delta}) = \int_{\Phi} \bar{U}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi}) p(\underline{\varphi}) d\underline{\varphi} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_z} w_i \int_{\Phi} \ln \frac{\Sigma_{z_i|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})}{\Sigma_{z_i}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})} p(\underline{\varphi}) d\underline{\varphi} \quad (23)$$

Using equal weight values $w_i = 1/n_z$, the utility function takes the form

$$U(\underline{\delta}) = -\frac{1}{2n_z} \int_{\Phi} \ln \prod_{i=1}^{n_z} \frac{\Sigma_{z_i|D}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})}{\Sigma_{z_i}(\underline{\delta}, \underline{\varphi})} p(\underline{\varphi}) d\underline{\varphi} \quad (24)$$

where $p(\underline{\varphi})$ is a probability distribution that is postulated to quantify the uncertainties in the values of model and input characteristics involved in $\underline{\varphi}$;

The utility function $U(\underline{\delta})$ represents the expected information gain from a sensor configuration $\underline{\delta}$ over all possible values of the model parameters $\underline{\varphi}$, weighted by the prior PDF $p(\underline{\varphi})$ of the model parameters. The multidimensional integral in Eq. (23) or Eq. (24) is a probability integral, which yields robust information gain by considering the uncertainty of the structural and noise parameters. The multidimensional integral can be evaluated using Monte Carlo techniques or sparse grid methods [74, 75].

The proposed approach is based on information theoretic formulation that results in optimizing in Eq. (22) a weighted sum of the logarithm of the variances of the error predicted by AKF for the input and/or output response time histories. Other approaches [28, 40–43] for input and response reconstruction use ad hoc measures (without any connection to established information theoretic measures), such as the sum of the variances, which is qualitatively different from the proposed approach. In addition, the proposed method maximizes the information gained during

the updating step of AKF (see Eq. (21)), using the error covariance of the prediction step of AKF as the prior estimate. This is not the same with existing methods [28, 40–43], which do not account for the prior information, resulting in a different objective function that is inconsistent with the information theory, especially when the expected utility function (23) is introduced as a measure of robustness to parameter uncertainties.

3.2. Optimal Sensor Placement

The optimal sensor configuration $\underline{\delta}_{opt}$ is obtained by maximizing the utility $U(\underline{\delta})$ with respect to the design variables $\underline{\delta}$, i.e.

$$\underline{\delta}_{opt} = \arg \max_{\underline{\delta}} U(\underline{\delta}) \quad (25)$$

The optimal number of sensors in the sensor configuration can be estimated by monitoring the information gain as additional sensors are placed in the structure. Usually, once sufficient number of sensors is placed, the information gain using additional sensors is relatively small and the process of adding sensors in the structure is terminated. The optimization problem is solved using discrete design variables associated with either the DOF where acceleration/displacement sensors are placed or the Gauss integration points where strain sensors are placed. To implement the discrete optimization algorithms for two types of sensors simultaneously, say N_a acceleration sensors and N_s strain sensors, we order the possible sensor locations in a new set containing all $N_{all} = N_a + N_s$ sensor locations consisting of 1 to N_a acceleration sensors and $N_a + 1$ to $N_a + N_s$ strain sensors and the optimization is then performed over the new set of N_{all} sensors. The optimization is performed using the SSP and/or GA algorithms.

3.2.1. Heuristic SSP Algorithms

Heuristic algorithms [39, 49, 57] have been used to effectively solve the optimization problem and provide near optimal solutions. Herein, the forward and backward sequential sensor placement (FSSP/BSSP) algorithms [49, 76] and the combined FSSP/BSSP algorithm [66], termed SSP, are used to provide near optima solutions [53]. Let N_0 be the number of sensors to be placed in the structure at N_{all} possible sensors positions. As demonstrated in the past [53], FSSP and BSSP algorithms offer systematic and computationally very efficient approaches for computing sequentially a near optimal sensor configuration involving 1 to N_0 sensors. Specifically, for the FSSP algorithm, given the positions of $(i - 1)$ sensors in the structure computed in the previous $(i - 1)$ steps, the position of the next i th sensor is obtained as the one, out of the remaining $(N_{all} - i + 1)$ possible sensor positions, that gives the highest increase in the information gain for i sensors, with the positions of the first $(i - 1)$ sensors fixed at the optimal ones already obtained in the previous $(i - 1)$ steps. This process starts for $i = 1$ and is continued for up to N_0 sensors. BSSP algorithm starts with N_{all} sensors placed at all possible position of the structure and proceeds by removing sequentially one sensor at a time from the position that results in the smallest decrease in the information gain. Given that i sensor remain in the structure after removing $N_{all} - i + 1$ sensors, the process of evaluating which sensor to remove from the remaining i positions involves evaluating i sensor configuration each one involving $i - 1$ sensors. This procedure is repeated, starting from $i = N_{all}$ until it terminates for $i = 2$. It should be noted that the FSSP provides the optimal sensor location for 1 up to N_0 sensors, while BSSP provides the optimal sensor configuration for 1 to N_{all} sensors.

The computational cost depends on the number of function evaluations and the floating-point operations involved in each function evaluation. Note that the floating-point operations for solving the Riccati Equation (Eq. (13)) is expected to increase as the number of sensors in a sensor

configuration increases. BSSP evaluates sensors configurations starting with as many as N_{all} sensors and sequentially removing 1 sensor at each step until a sensor configuration with 1 sensor is reached. Conversely, FSSP evaluates sensor configurations starting with 1 sensor and sequentially adding a sensor until a sensor configuration with N_0 sensors is reached.

For $N_{all} > N_0$, i.e. for the case that the number of sensors to be placed in the structure is small compared to the number of possible sensor positions, usually the case in structural dynamics applications, the use of BSSP to obtain results has the effect of raising substantially the computational cost as compared to FSSP. Thus, from the computational point of view, the FSSP algorithm should be the preferred algorithm in applications. However, the estimates from the two algorithms are expected to differ due to the fact that both algorithms are heuristic and provide approximate values.

To increase the reliability of the estimates arising from the two heuristic algorithms, the final solution is taken from the combination of the FSSP and BSSP solutions, referred as the SSP estimate. Specifically, for each sensor configuration containing a fixed number of sensors, the final maximum utility value is taken to be $U_{max} = \max(U_{F,max}, U_{B,max})$, where $U_{F,max}$ and $U_{B,max}$ are the maximum values estimated from the FSSP and BSSP algorithms, respectively. Additionally, the optimal sensor placement is selected among the FSSP and BSSP optimal sensor placement that corresponds to the value of U_{max} . A similar procedure is used for the minimum utility value, i.e., $U_{min} = \max(U_{F,min}, U_{B,min})$.

3.2.2. System Inversion Conditions

The proposed method is functional only if the foregoing Riccati equation leads to a unique bounded solution. Thus, the existence of such a solution for Eq. (13) should be viewed as a prerequisite for the OSP. This condition should be checked based on the system inversion requirements, specified by the following theorem.

Theorem 1. The dynamical system characterized by (1) and (2) is instantaneously invertible if and only if $\text{rank}(J) = n_u$ [52].

A proof for this theorem can be found in [77]. An important consequence of this theorem is that at least acceleration sensors should be placed on the structure to satisfy the invertibility conditions. By satisfying this condition, the Riccati equation is expected to return a bounded positive-definite solution. Additionally, when FSSP is used to compute the best sensor configuration, in order to meet the AKF invertibility conditions for n_u input loads, the first n_u sensors are required to be acceleration sensors placed at their optimal positions. Similarly, when the worst sensor configuration is computed, the first n_u sensors are selected to be acceleration sensors placed at their worst positions.

3.2.3. Genetic Algorithms (GA)

Genetic algorithms can also be used with discrete design variables to estimate the optimal sensor locations as well as the type of sensors to be combined. In this work, the GA routine in Matlab is used for optimizing the location of N_0 sensors, consisting of acceleration and/or strain sensors. In this case, there are N_0 discrete-valued design variables with the values of each one constrained to be a lower bound of 1 and an upper bound of N_{all} . In order to meet the AKF stability conditions, for the case where both acceleration and strain sensors are used simultaneously, the first N_p design variables out of the N_0 design variables are constrained to involve acceleration sensors only by allowing the values of the design variable to vary from 1 to N_a , excluding the values of $N_a + 1$ to N_{all} that correspond to strain sensors.

In Matlab GA routine the parameters are encoded in real format. Matlab GA routine uses elitism, selecting individuals having lower fitness value in the current population as elite and passes them to the next population. For the number of 'elite children' the Matlab default value is used. The maximum population size is selected according to the number of sensors N_0 . The maximum generation size is selected to be high and the tolerance value small to be able to prevent premature termination of the optimization. Specifically, the GA is carried out using a population size of $10 \times N_0$ and maximum generations of 10000. GA stops if the average relative change in the best fitness function value is less than a tolerance value selected as 10^{-8} .

3.3. State, Observation and Prediction Errors

The covariance R of the observation error is assumed to be diagonal with the (i, i) component $R^{(ii)}$ given in the form [66, 76, 78]

$$R^{(ii)} = s^2 + \sigma_e^2 Q_y^{(ii)} \quad (26)$$

where $Q_y^{(ii)}$ is the square of the intensity of the QoI y_i at DOF i . The first term accounts for the measurement error and its value is considered to be independent of the response intensity, with the level s of the measurement error to depend on the sensor accuracy and characteristics. The second term accounts for the modelling errors with the error at DOF i selected to be proportional to the variance $Q_y^{(ii)}$ of the square of the intensity of the observed QoI y_i at DOF i . The parameter σ_e denote the levels of modelling errors in relation to the intensity of the QoI. Spatial correlation between the errors in the two measured QoI has also been introduced [76] to avoid sensor clustering due to the redundant information provided by closely spaced sensors measuring the same QoI. More details about the choice of the observation error and the rationale behind it can be found in a number of previous works on the subject [66, 76, 78].

A similar formulation can be used for the variance R_{ε_i} involved in Eq. (16) of the error ε_i for the predicted QoI z_i . In this case, only the modelling errors exists and the i -th diagonal element of the covariance matrix can be selected to be

$$R_{\varepsilon_i} = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 Q_{z_i} \quad (27)$$

where Q_{z_i} is the square of the intensity of the predicted QoI $z_i(t)$, and σ_ε is the level of modelling errors adjusted in relation to the intensity of the predicted QoI.

The process noise covariance matrix Q is defined based on the magnitude of the state vector

$$Q = \sigma_x^2 \text{diag}(Q_x) \quad (28)$$

where the standard deviation σ_x controls the order of magnitude of error, while the input force vector error covariance matrix S is defined based on the magnitude of the input intensity

$$S = \alpha^2 \text{diag}(Q_u) \quad (29)$$

which signifies that the random walk fluctuations of the input is a fraction α of the input intensity.

4. Applications

A square plate structure (Figure 1) modeled by thin-shell FEs is used to demonstrate the methodology. The length of the side of the plate is $1m$ and the thickness is $2mm$. The plate is fixed at the left edge. Its density is $11000kg/mm^3$, the modulus of elasticity is $E = 9e + 10Pa$ and the Poisson's ratio is $\nu = 0.3$. The FE model is meshed with eight-node shell elements, containing

six DOF per node. The mesh consists of 420 elements and 441 nodes. Linear elastic behavior is considered. For demonstration purposes, it is assumed that only the lowest eight modes contribute to the response. The lowest eight natural frequencies of the FE model are presented in Table 1. The modal damping ratios for all contributing modes are taken to be equal to 2%. The optimal location of acceleration and/or strain sensors is obtained for the purpose of predicting strains in the structure.

Figure 1: Square thin plate with left edge fixed (shown in red line), meshed with 8-node square elements. The load is applied at point A (right bottom corner) perpendicular to the plate’s surface.

Table 1: Contributing modal frequencies of the plate.

Mode	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3	Mode 4	Mode 5	Mode 6	Mode 7	Mode 8
Natural Frequency (Hz)	0.956	2.34	5.90	7.52	8.56	14.99	17.18	17.90

4.1. Selection of Process/Plant, Measurement, Model/Prediction and Load Error Parameters

It is assumed that the plate is subjected to a concentrated load applied at the right bottom corner A shown in Figure 1. The effect of the values of the process/plant, measurement and prediction error covariance matrices Q , R and R_ε on the optimal sensor placement for reliable response reconstruction is investigated in this work. For this, to study the effect of small, moderate and large errors, it is required to carefully select the quantities appearing in the definition of Q , R and R_ε in Eqs. (28), (26) and (27), respectively. Specifically, the quantities Q_x , $Q_y^{(ii)}$ and Q_{z_i} are selected based on a nominal broadband excitation applied at point A, modeled by a Gaussian white noise sequence with standard deviation σ_{wn} . Estimates of the intensities (root mean square) of the accelerations at the DOF perpendicular to the xy plane (plate surface) and the normal strains along the x direction on the upper plate surface are then readily obtained. Specifically, for a scalar discrete stationary zero-mean Gaussian white noise excitation $\underline{u}(t)$ with variance σ_{wn}^2 , the covariance matrix Q_z of the response QoI \underline{z} defined in Eq. (3) with $\varepsilon_k = 0$ is given by

$$Q_z = \sigma_{wn}^2 (\tilde{G} \bar{Q}_x \tilde{G}^T + \tilde{J} S \tilde{J}^T) \quad (30)$$

while the covariance matrix Q_x of the state vector \underline{x}_k is given by $Q_x = \sigma_{wn}^2 \bar{Q}_x$, where using Eq. (1) under stationary conditions and with $\underline{w}_k = 0$, the covariance matrix Q_x can be obtained by

solving the discrete Liapunov equation

$$A\bar{Q}_xA^T - \bar{Q}_x + BB^T = 0 \quad (31)$$

The estimated value of Q_x is used in Eq. (28), the value of Q_z is used in Eq. (27), while the value of Q_y in Eq. (26) is obtained by setting $z = y$ in Eq. (30).

The value of σ_e of the modelling errors in Eq. (26) and the values of σ_ϵ of the prediction error in Eq. (27) are selected to be $\sigma_e = \sigma_\epsilon = 0.001, 0.01$ and 0.1 corresponding to a small, moderate and large modelling error. To complete the formulation for the errors, one needs to select the values of the measurement error parameter s in Eq. (26). For this, the intensities of the acceleration at all nodes and the strains for all FEs along the x direction of the plate surface are shown in Figure 2, normalized by the strength σ_{wn} of the white noise. The selected values of the measurement error parameter s corresponding to three cases of small, moderate and measurement errors are given in Table 2 for acceleration and strain sensors. In Table 2, ϵ_{min} is the minimum value of the strain and acceleration that covers 98% of the plate surface. The values in the table for moderate error indicate that the measurement error parameter s is selected in a way that it corresponds to the 1% – 2% of the average value of the intensity of the response QoI (acceleration or strain). Finally, the value of the covariance matrix S is selected to be $S = 1$, which for the nominal white noise excitation used it corresponds to $\sigma_{wn} = 1$.

Figure 2: Intensities of (a) accelerations and (b) strains when the plate analysed is subjected to a discrete zero-mean white noise input sequence applied at point A, with standard deviation equal to 1.

Table 2: Modelling, measurement and prediction errors, process noise, and load model error parameters. ϵ_{min} is the minimum value of the nodal accelerations or element strains that cover 98% of the plate surface. ϵ_{max} and ϵ_{rms} are respectively the maximum value and the intensity (root mean square) of the nodal acceleration or element strain in the plate surface.

Error	Sensor type	$\sigma_e, \sigma_\epsilon$	s	s/ϵ_{rms}	s/ϵ_{min}	s/ϵ_{max}	σ_x	α
Small	Acceleration	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	1.4×10^{-2}	2.7×10^{-4}	10^{-3}	1
Small	Strain	10^{-3}	10^{-8}	1.6×10^{-3}	10^{-2}	5.6×10^{-4}	10^{-3}	1
Moderate	Acceleration	10^{-2}	10^{-2}	10^{-2}	1.4×10^{-1}	2.7×10^{-3}	10^{-3}	1
Moderate	Strain	10^{-2}	10^{-7}	1.6×10^{-2}	10^{-1}	5.6×10^{-3}	10^{-3}	1
Large	Acceleration	10^{-1}	10^{-1}	10^{-1}	1.4×10^0	2.7×10^{-2}	10^{-3}	1
Large	Strain	10^{-1}	10^{-6}	1.6×10^{-1}	10^0	5.6×10^{-2}	10^{-3}	1

4.2. Strain Predictions Using a Combination of Acceleration and Strain Observations

The positions of the acceleration and strain sensors are optimized for reliable strain prediction in all 400 FEs of the plate. The strain sensors are assumed to be placed at the midpoint of each FE, measuring the normal strain along the x direction on the plate surface.

Taking into account that a single load at A is applied, the system inversion conditions dictates that at least one acceleration sensor is required. Thus, in the optimization procedure, the first sensor is forced to be an acceleration sensor.

4.2.1. Information Gain versus Number of Sensors

The utility results estimated using GA and SSP algorithms as a function of the number of sensors are given in Figure 3 for up to 30 sensors for the moderate error case presented in Table 2. The maximum information U_{max}^{all} that can be reached (shown by horizontal line in Figure 3a) is calculated by assuming that 420 acceleration and 400 strain sensors are placed at all possible locations. Comparing the utility values calculated by the SSP and the GA algorithm, it can be seen that very similar maximum utility values are obtained for most of the sensor numbers in a sensor configuration (Figure 3a). For less than 9 sensors the GA is more accurate than the SSP method. The SSP algorithm gives overall higher utility values for 9 or more sensors, demonstrating in this case an improved accuracy compared to the GA algorithm. However, it is expected that the estimates from the GA algorithm can be improved at a higher computational cost if one uses lower tolerance values for stopping the GA algorithm.

Figure 3: (a) Utility values, and (b) normalized utility values. The maximum utility is obtained by using 820 acceleration and strain sensors, 400 strain sensors, and 420 acceleration sensors, placed at all possible positions, is shown with black, red, and blue horizontal lines, respectively.

Observing the utility values as a function of the number of sensors, it is seen that the information gain increases as additional sensors are placed at their optimal locations. Significant information is gained by each additional sensor for up to 9 sensors placed in the structure. Adding more than 9 sensors, the information gain for each additional sensor placed in the structure is relatively small compared to the information gained for the first nine sensors. Normalized utility values obtained by dividing the utility values in Figure 3a by the maximum utility value that can be achieved by placing the maximum number of 420 acceleration and 400 strain sensors are presented in Figure 3b. Tracking the maximum normalized information gain values as a function of the number of sensors

helps decide on the number of sensors to be kept in a sensor configuration. The number of sensors is considered to be adequate when the maximum information gained is a large percentage of the maximum information U_{max}^{all} or the information gained by each additional sensors is not significant compared to the information gained by the existing sensors. Based on the results in Figure 3b, it is reasonable to use 9 sensors placed at their optimal positions since the information gained is 91% of U_{max}^{all} and the increase in information gain by adding a sensor at a time is relatively small. Such information gain should be weighted with the cost of the information [67] so that a cost-effective and highly informative sensor configuration is obtained.

Comparison of FSSP, BSSP and GA algorithms can be seen in Figure 4. It is evident that the GA algorithm also provides a near optimal solution, as the heuristic FSSP and BSSP algorithms do. The BSSP provides the best accuracy for 9 or more sensors, while GA provides more accurate solutions for less than 9 sensors. The FSSP gives better accuracy than BSSP for less than 9 sensors. The GA estimate depends on the tolerance values used. Improving this estimate using lower tolerance values for stopping the algorithm may be computationally a very costly procedure.

Figure 4: Comparison of FSSP, BSSP, M-BSSP and GA. (a) Maximum utility values, and (b) minimum utility values. The max utility obtained by using 820 acceleration and strain sensors, 400 strain sensors, and 420 acceleration sensors, placed at all possible positions, is shown with black, red, and blue horizontal lines, respectively.

The time-to-solution (TTS) required for estimating the optimal and worst sensor placement results for 1 to 30 sensors from the different algorithms is given in Table 3. From the results, the following points can be made:

- The FSSP method is computationally efficient, while the BSSP method can be inefficient if the number of possible sensor positions N_{all} is large.
- The computational efficiency of GA is significantly less than FSSP and higher than BSSP. However, the computational cost for BSSP can be drastically improved by starting with a configuration that involves significantly a smaller number of sensors N_{start} selected to be higher than the number N_0 of sensors to be optimized.
- The starting sensor configuration with N_{start} sensors must be selected to be optimal. Such sensor configuration can be obtained using the FSSP or the GA algorithm. Following this

procedure, results from the modified BSSP (M-BSSP) algorithm for $N_{start} = 100$ and 200, instead of 820, are given in Table 3 and also in Figure 4 for $N_{start} = 100$. As shown, the estimates of the utility values almost coincide with those of the original BSSP algorithm.

- For $N_{start} = 100$, the total TTS of M-BSSP for 1-100 sensors is the sum of required time to run FSSP (5 min) and the running time of BSSP (0.7 min).
- For optimizing 100 sensors through the GA, the TTS drops to 1 min (0.7 min to compute the optimal sensor configuration for 1-100 sensors using BSSP and 0.3 min to run the GA for 100 sensors). This time is approximately the same as the TTS required to compute the optimal sensor configuration for 1-30 sensors using FSSP. As a result, the computational time using M-BSSP is approximately two to three orders of magnitude less than the computational time of 842 min required for the original BSSP algorithm.

Table 3: Time-to-solution (TTS) for computing the optimal and worst sensor configurations for 1 to 30 sensors from different algorithms.

Method	FSSP	BSSP	SSP	GA	FSSP	GA	M-BSSP	FSSP	GA	M-BSSP
Sensors	1-30	1-30	1-30	1-30	1-100	100	1-100	1-200	200	1-200
TTS (min)	1	842	843	32	5	0.3	0.7	14	0.1	3

4.2.2. Optimal Location of Acceleration and Strain Sensors

Figure 5a shows the best acceleration (circle) and strain (square) sensor locations (estimated using GA and SSP algorithms) for 9 sensors. For SSP results, the best type of sensors to be used are 5 acceleration sensors and 4 strain sensors out of the total of 9 sensors. The 4 strain sensors are placed on the plate at a reasonable distance from each other and far from the right edge which has a very small strain intensity and so the noise-to-signal ratio is expected to be large. The acceleration sensors are placed closer to the right edge, far away from the fixed support, since there again the noise-to-signal ratio is expected to be smaller than places close to the fixed support. Similar results in terms of the number and location of the acceleration and strain sensors are obtained using GA, promoting 5 acceleration sensors and 4 strain sensors. For the worst sensor positions (Figure 5b), SSP and GA results are consistent in terms of showing that nine acceleration sensors (no strain sensors) placed close to the left edge, where the noise-to-signal ratio in acceleration time histories is large, will give the worst strain predictions.

Figure 5: (a) Best 9 sensor positions, and (b) worst 9 sensor positions.

The optimal sensor configuration for 6 sensors is found to involve 4 acceleration sensors and 2 strain sensors. It is worth noting that the maximum information gain that can be achieved for 6 sensors is 3.06 (see Figure 3), which is slightly higher than the maximum information gained with 420 acceleration sensors placed at all possible positions (blue horizontal line in Figure 3). This case of a small number of 6 sensors is used to point out that a combination of the two types of sensors (4 strain and 2 acceleration sensors) optimally placed in the structure can provide better information than the one obtained from a sensor configuration involving a very large number of the same type of acceleration sensors.

It should be pointed out that based on the utility values presented in Figure 3, the SSP results for the optimal sensor configuration are slightly more informative than the GA results. Nevertheless, it is expected that both algorithms will give reasonable near optimum sensor configurations. The observed variability in the near optimal sensor configuration between the predictions from the SSP and GA algorithms is due to the fact that among all $4.4e+20$ possible sensor configurations of 9 sensors placed at 820 positions, a small fraction of them give near optimum solutions. This small fraction can be a large number of sensor configurations that are promoted by the SSP and GA algorithms used.

The AKF method for response reconstruction and virtual sensing is able to fuse acceleration and strain sensors. Despite the fact that the predictions are strains throughout the plate, the type of sensors that are promoted for monitoring are both acceleration and strain sensors. In contrast, the optimal sensor placement based on modal expansion [66] limits the type of sensors that can be used. For example, for strain predictions, only strain or displacement sensors can be used.

4.2.3. Effect of Measurement and Modelling Errors

The effect of the measurement and modelling errors on the OSP results is next investigated. OSP results for small, moderate, and large measurement errors are obtained by selecting the values of the error covariance matrix parameter s (in Eq. (26)) to vary as indicated in Table 2 and letting the modelling error parameters to be $\sigma_e = \sigma_\varepsilon = 0.01$, corresponding to moderate modelling error.

The utility results for the three measurement error cases estimated using the M-BSSP and GA algorithms are presented in Figure 6. Similar results for moderate measurement error are compared

in Figure 7 for three different values of the modelling error selected to be $\sigma_e = \sigma_\epsilon = 10^{-3}$ (small modelling error), 10^{-2} (moderate modelling error) and 10^{-1} (large modelling error). It is clear that the information gain decreases as the measurement error or the model error increases, signifying that less information is gained from noisy measurements or less accurate models.

Figure 6: Comparison of utility (information gain) results for different measurement error cases. Color and black symbols represent results obtained from M-BSSP and GA algorithms, respectively. (a) Utility values, (b) normalized utility values. The max utility obtained by using 820 acceleration and strain sensors, 400 strain sensors, and 420 acceleration sensors, placed at all possible positions, is shown with black horizontal lines.

Figure 7: Comparison of utility (information gain) results for different modelling error cases. Color and black symbols represent results obtained from M-BSSP and GA algorithms, respectively. (a) Utility values, (b) normalized utility values. The max utility obtained by using 820 acceleration and strain sensors, 400 strain sensors, and 420 acceleration sensors, placed at all possible positions, is shown with black horizontal lines.

For small to moderate measurement errors (see Figure 6b), nine sensors placed at their optimal location account for 95% to 90% approximately of the maximum information U_{\max}^{all} that can be

achieved by adding 820 strain and acceleration sensors at all possible locations. In contrast, for large measurement error the information gain that can be achieved with 9 sensors placed at their optimal locations is 65% of the maximum information gain U_{\max}^{all} . This significantly lower information extracted from the measurements is due to the higher noise to signal ratio in the measurements. Specifically, more sensors are needed to extract significant information, with 30 sensors providing only 75% of U_{\max}^{all} . The higher the measurement error, the less the information extracted from the sensors, which is consistent with the results obtained from a similar work based on modal expansion technique for response reconstruction [66].

Similar observations can be made for the different model errors. The higher the model error, the less the information gained from a sensor configuration involving a fixed number of sensors. There is, however, a qualitative difference for the effect of the number of sensors on the information gain for the two different types of errors. As the measurement error increases, the maximum information gain U_{all}^{\max} that can be achieved with 820 strain and acceleration sensors does not deteriorate significantly as can be seen by the horizontal lines in Figure 6a. However, increasing the measurement error to large values, the information gained by using 9 sensors is only 60% of U_{\max}^{all} , and a large number of sensors are required to gain the remaining 40% of the information. In contrast, increasing the model error to large values (Figure 7a), the maximum information gain that can be achieved with 820 strain and acceleration sensors reduces substantially to 60% and 45% of the maximum information gained for moderate and small model error values, respectively.

On the other hand, for large model error, a large percentage, around 94%, of the maximum information gain U_{all}^{\max} , can be achieved with as many as 9 sensors placed at their optimal locations. Adding more sensors from 10 to 820 will only result in a very small increase (5%) in the maximum information gain.

Thus, for high model error, a small number of sensors placed at their optimal locations will obtain most of the information that can be achieved by fully populating the structure with sensors. This is due to the fact that predictions with very low or very high intensity contain the same large percentage of model error in relation to their intensity. For high enough model error (the case in Figure 7a), the model error dominates the measurement error, with each sensor contributing significant information from 1 up to 9 sensors. For more than 9 sensors, the addition of more sensors does not provide any significant information due to the fact that all remaining possible sensor locations are contaminated by the same level of large model error, regardless of the intensity of the predictions at the sensor locations. This means that there is no more information to be gained by adding sensors at any position.

The optimal sensor positions for nine sensors obtained using the combined M-BSSP estimates are compared for the different values of the measurement errors and moderate model error in Figure 8a and for moderate measurement error and different values of model error in 8b. For small measurement errors in Figure 8a, the strain sensors are placed towards the right edge of the plate where, although the strains are relatively small, the noise to signal ratio is small and the quality of information is very good. For large measurement errors in Figure 8a, placing strain sensors in the right edge is avoided since the signal to noise ratio for strains decreases and the quality of information from strain sensors placed towards the right edge is substantially deteriorated. In addition, for the large error case, the strain sensors towards the right edge tend to be replaced by acceleration sensors. The worst sensors are found to be acceleration sensors (not shown in the figures) for all error cases placed at the nodes closest to the left support.

From Figure 8b it can be seen that there is not a clear trend in the placement of sensors for different levels of model error. One does not expect to have the tendency observed with increasing measurement error since the model error, quantified at each point in the plate as a fixed error with

respect to the intensity of the measured/predicted QoI at this point, is set to be the same over the whole surface. So locations with higher or lower signal-to-noise ratio should not be preferred.

Figure 8: Comparison of best sensor locations for 9 sensors using M-BSSP (a) for different measurement error cases, (b) for different modelling error cases. Acceleration and strain sensors are shown with circle and square, respectively.

4.2.4. Robustness to Measurement and Modelling Error Uncertainties

The level of noise to signal ratio are not known a priori since the intensity and frequency content of the excitation and thus the level of measured response is not known. The size of modelling and prediction errors due to unmodelled dynamics is also not known a priori. Thus, it is more rational to use a robust design to better account for uncertainty in measurements, the structural model and prediction errors. Two robust designs $R1$ and $R2$ are next considered. In robust design $R1$, the uncertainties for measurement errors are considered by letting $s = 10^\beta$ and assigning a uniform prior distribution of the measurement error parameter β with large enough bounds, given by $\beta \sim U(-8, -6)$ for strain sensors and $\beta \sim U(-3, -1)$ for acceleration sensors, covering the domain in the parameter space that correspond to small, moderate and large measurement errors. The uncertain parameter space has dimension two since it involves one parameter for the measurement error for accelerations and one parameter for strains. Similarly, in robust design $R2$, the uncertainties for modelling errors are considered by letting $\sigma_e = \sigma_\epsilon = 10^\gamma$ and assigning a uniform prior distribution of the modelling error parameter γ with large enough bounds, given by $\gamma \sim U(-3, -1)$ for strain and acceleration sensors, covering the domain in the parameter space that corresponds to small, moderate and large modelling errors. The uncertain parameter space has dimension one. OSP robust results are calculated for moderate measurement error using the sparse grid algorithm of order 10.

The number of strain and acceleration sensors estimated for each optimal sensor configuration for N_0 ranging from 1 to 30 for the two robust cases $R1$ and $R2$ are compared in Figure 9 with the ones obtained for the deterministic case for moderate modelling and measurement error. It can be seen that there is an increase in strain sensors in the robust case $R1$ compared to the strain sensors required in the deterministic case. The number of acceleration sensors in the robust case $R1$ is two for all values of $N_0 > 1$ considered. Also for the robust case $R2$, there is no clear change

in the number of strain and acceleration sensors in a sensor configuration when compared to the deterministic case. The optimal sensor configuration obtained for 1 to 30 sensors for the robust case $R1$ (or the robust case $R2$), is used to estimate the utility values, denoted by U_s^{R1} , U_m^{R1} and U_l^{R1} (or U_s^{R2} , U_m^{R2} and U_l^{R2}) for the three deterministic cases corresponding to small, moderate and large measurement error, respectively. The ratio $U_s^{R1,2}/U_s^{max}$, $U_m^{R1,2}/U_m^{max}$ and $U_l^{R1,2}/U_l^{max}$ of the computed utility values to the maximum utility values U_s^{max} , U_m^{max} and U_l^{max} for the deterministic cases for small, moderate and measurement (respectively modelling) errors are shown in Figure 10. Such ratios provide the percentage of information gain that the robust OSP can achieve for the three measurement or modelling error cases in relation to the maximum information gain that could be achieved by the three deterministic cases. The closeness of these values to unity indicates the effectiveness of the OSP robust case when applied to the three deterministic cases of small, moderate and large error. It can be seen that the robust case is effective for large modelling or measurement errors. Decreasing these errors, the effectiveness of the robust cases deteriorates, reaching information gain values that are as low as 88% of the information entropy values that can be achieved by the OSP obtained for the deterministic cases.

Figure 9: Number of acceleration sensors and total number of sensors versus number of sensors for deterministic and robust cases $R1$ and $R2$. The number of strain sensors is the difference between the total number of sensors and the number of acceleration sensors.

Figure 10: Ratios $U_s^{R1,2}/U_s^{max}$, $U_m^{R1,2}/U_m^{max}$ and $U_l^{R1,2}/U_l^{max}$ for the robust cases $R1$ and $R2$, computed using (a) GA for 1 to 8 sensors, and (b) M-BSSP for 9 to 30 sensors.

4.2.5. Robustness to Damping Ratio Uncertainties

In this section, we study to what extent the pre-selected modal damping ratios can influence the sensors position and the utility. For this purpose, the modal damping ratios are considered independent and each one of them is described through uniform distribution $U(0.01, 0.05)$, allowed to vary within the practical range 1% to 5%. Then, OSP has been performed considering the uncertainty of the modal damping ratios using 1000 Monte Carlo samples to approximate the integral in Eq. (24). Figure 11 demonstrates the normalized utility and the sensor placement for the robust design R3, obtained by the M-BSSP algorithm while considering the uncertainty of the damping ratios. This figure also compares the results with the case where the modal damping ratios are fixed at 2%, as indicated by the label *deterministic*. It is notable that the maximum and minimum utilities are slightly smaller for the robust design R3 when compared to the deterministic case. Moreover, the optimal location of sensors remains almost the same, regardless of the damping ratio uncertainty.

Figure 11: OSP results for fixed and uncertain damping ratio cases, obtained using M-BSSP. (a) Normalized utility values, (b) Best sensor position. The max utility obtained by using 400 strain sensors, and 420 acceleration sensors, placed at all possible positions, is shown with black horizontal lines; Acceleration and strain sensors are shown with circle and square, respectively. OSP with a fixed damping ratio value of 0.02 is shown with red colour; OSP for uncertain damping ratio is shown in purple.

4.3. OSP for Strain Prediction using Acceleration-Only or Strain-Only Measurements

Next, the optimal sensor placement for reliable strain prediction in all 400 FEs is performed using either acceleration or strain sensors. For optimally locating acceleration sensors, the maximum utility results calculated using SSP and GA algorithms are given in Figure 12a for moderate modelling and measurement error (see Table 2) as a function of the number of sensors. For 8 or more sensors, the utility values found by the SSP and the GA algorithms are almost the same (Figure 12a). For 5 to 7 sensors, the GA algorithm is more accurate providing slightly higher values than the ones predicted by SSP. It is apparent that the optimal number of acceleration sensors is 8 placed at their optimal positions since the information gain is almost the same as the information gained by populating the plate with as many as 420 acceleration sensors at all possible locations. Comparing the maximum information gain U_{all}^{max} in Figure 12a with the one in Figure 3a, it can be seen that an optimal sensor configuration consisting of a combination of strain and acceleration sensors provides significantly higher information than an optimal sensor configuration consisting of acceleration sensors only.

Figure 12: Comparison of SSP and GA. Utility values obtained by (a) acceleration sensors, (b) strain sensors. The max utility values obtained by using acceleration or strain sensors placed at all possible positions are shown with a horizontal line (420 acceleration sensors in (a), 400 strain sensors (with one acceleration) in (b)).

The maximum utility values as a function of strain sensors optimally located in the plate are given in Figure 12b. To maintain stability of the Kalman filter, the positions of the strain sensors are optimized by introducing an acceleration sensor at the input location. For 8 or more strain sensors, the utility values estimated by SSP are slightly higher than the ones estimated by GA, while for less than 8 sensors GA provides slightly better results than SSP. Comparing the results in Figure 12b for strain sensors and 1 acceleration sensor at the load location, with the ones in Figure 3a for a combination of strain and acceleration sensors optimally placed in the structure, the information gain obtained using strain sensors only (and 1 acceleration sensor) is not significantly less than the information provided by sensor configurations consisting of a combination of optimally placed acceleration and strain sensors. As a result, in contrast to the significantly less informative sensor configurations consisting of acceleration sensors (compare Figure 12a with Figure 3a), sensor configurations involving strain sensors only (and one acceleration sensor to maintain filter stability) can provide almost as good information as the combination of strain and acceleration sensors (compare Figure 12b and Figure 3a). However, installation, calibration and maintenance complexities involved with strain sensors make their use less favorable than acceleration sensors. Thus, a combination of acceleration and strain sensors is the most preferred sensor configuration as presented in subsection 4.2.

The TTS required for optimizing the acceleration or the strain sensors for 1 to 30 sensors from different algorithms is given in Table 4. The TTS for computing the optimal and worst locations of acceleration sensors is 17 min for SSP algorithm (0.7 min for FSSP) and 30 min for GA algorithm. The TTS for computing the optimal and worst locations of strain sensors is 32 min with SSP (0.7 min for FSSP) and 18 min with GA algorithm. The computational effort for SSP (combination of FSSP and BSSP) algorithm can be substantially reduced by one to two orders of magnitude by using M-BSSP algorithm with $N_{start} = 100$ sensors. Specifically, the TTS for acceleration sensors drops from 17 min for SSP to 3.1 and 0.7 min for M-BSSP using respectively FSSP and GA algorithm to compute the starting sensor configuration for $N_{start} = 100$ sensors, while for strain sensors drops from 32 min for SSP to 3.1 and 0.7 min for M-BSSP using respectively FSSP and GA algorithm to compute the starting sensor configuration for $N_{start} = 100$ sensors. The

results reveal that the FSSP method is computationally very efficient, while the BSSP method can be inefficient if the number of possible sensor positions N_{all} is large, leading to computational effort that might exceed that of GA algorithm. The proposed M-BSSP algorithm exploits the computational efficiency of FSSP and the accuracy of BSSP. These results are consistent with the results reported in Table 3. Comparing the computational savings gained using M-BSSP in Table 3 for $N_{all} = 820$ and Table 4 for $N_{all} = 400$ or 420 , it can be concluded that higher savings are expected as N_{all} increases.

Table 4: Time-to-solution (TTS) for computing the optimal and worst sensor configurations for 1 to 30 acceleration only or strain only sensors from different algorithms.

Method	FSSP	BSSP	SSP	GA	FSSP	GA	M-BSSP	FSSP	GA	M-BSSP
Sensors	1-30	1-30	1-30	1-30	1-100	100	1-100	1-200	200	1-200
TTS (min) - Accel. sensors	0.7	16	17	30	2.5	0.1	0.6	5.4	0.1	2.6
TTS (min) - Strain sensors	0.7	31	32	18	2.5	0.1	0.6	5.6	0.1	2

The best sensor locations for 8 sensors obtained using the GA and SSP algorithms are given in Figure 13a for acceleration sensors only and in Figure 13b for strain sensors only. For each case, both SSP and GA provide qualitatively similar sensor positions. The acceleration sensors are distributed towards to the right edge which has higher acceleration intensity and thus low noise to signal ratio. Similarly, the strain sensors are distributed towards the left edge since the strain values are higher and the noise to signal ratio is low.

Figure 13: (a) Best 8 acceleration sensor positions, (b) best 8 strain sensor positions.

4.4. Optimal Sensor Configuration for Input Estimation

The optimal design of sensor configuration for input reconstruction is next considered. The maximum and minimum information gain values estimated by the M-BSSP algorithm as a function of the number of sensors is given in Figure 14a. These values are compared with the maximum and minimum information gain values estimated for strain response predictions. A similar trend is

observed, although the maximum information gain for input estimation is less than the maximum information gain for strain response predictions. In contrast to the strain response predictions where 9 sensors provide more than 90% of the maximum information U_{\max}^{all} , 7-9 sensors and as many as 30 sensors optimally placed for input estimation provide approximately 70% and 80% of the U_{\max}^{all} , respectively. One needs more than 30 sensors to achieve an information gain higher than 90% of the U_{\max}^{all} .

Comparison of the optimal sensor configurations involving 9 sensors for input and response reconstruction is shown in Figure 14b. The optimal sensor configurations present some differences which are expected, since the objectives differ in the two design cases. Figure 14a also includes the information gain values $U_s(\delta_{in})$ for the strain predictions for 1 to 30 sensors that can be achieved for the sensor configuration optimally designed for reconstructing the input. Similarly, the information gain curve $U_{in}(\delta_s)$ for input estimation that can be achieved for the sensor configuration optimally designed for estimating strains is also presented. It can be seen that in both cases of the optimal sensor configuration for a design objective is suboptimal for another design objective. The information loss is of the order of approximately 20% loss.

Figure 14: Comparison of OSP results for strain or input reconstruction. (a) utility values, (b) best sensor positions found by M-BSSP. The maximum utility obtained by using 820 acceleration and strain sensors, 400 strain sensors, and 420 acceleration sensors, placed at all possible positions, is shown with black lines. Red and purple colours refers to OSP for strain and input prediction, respectively. $U_s(\delta_{in})$ (respectively $U_{in}(\delta_s)$) is the information gain for the strain (respectively input) reconstruction using the sensor configuration optimally designed for reconstructing the input (respectively strain).

4.5. Effectiveness of Optimal Sensor Configuration for Response Predictions

The effectiveness of the best sensor configuration is next investigated using simulated measurements. For this, a white noise input at location A (Figure 1) is first used to simulate strain response time histories at all FEs considering up to eight contributing modes. The standard deviation of the Gaussian white noise sequence is set to $\sigma_{wn} = 1$. A sampling period of $\Delta t = 0.01$ seconds and a response duration of 10 seconds are used to generate the simulated time histories. To simulate noise contaminated measurements and thus consider the effect of the measurement error (noise from sensors), independent zero-mean Gaussian white noise sequences with standard

deviation equal to 2% of the intensity of the simulated response is added to each simulated strain response time history.

The relative errors between the strain responses predicted by AKF with a fixed number of sensors and the simulated, noise contaminated measurements are used to demonstrate the effectiveness of the optimal sensor configuration in the presence of measurement error. The relative strain error at each location is defined as the ratio of the root mean square error between the predicted and measured responses over the root mean square value (intensity) of the measured strain response time history. The relative errors for the strain predictions obtained using AKF for 9 best sensor positions found by SSP algorithm for moderate measurement and modelling errors are presented in Figures 15a. The information gain for the best sensor configuration is 91% of U_{\max} . These errors should be compared with the relative errors shown in Figure 15b, obtained using 9 sensors placed at arbitrarily selected sensor positions and corresponding to lower utility value of 68% of U_{\max} . It is clear that the errors for the arbitrarily selected sensor configuration are significantly higher than the ones for the optimal sensor configuration. In particular, the average relative error over the plate surface is 4.23% for the arbitrary sensor configuration, which should be compared to the average relative error of 1.67% for the optimal sensor configuration. The average relative errors computed between input time history predicted by AKF and the simulated input are found to be 16.21% and 11.87% for the arbitrary and optimal sensor configuration, respectively. These higher errors are consistent with the finding in Section 4.4 where optimal sensor placement for response reconstruction is suboptimal for input reconstruction and that a small number of sensors (9 sensors in this case) contain 60% of the maximum information gain that can be achieved by fully populating the plate with sensors. In general, the aforementioned results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed OSP methodology.

Figure 15: Relative errors in strain response for white noise excitation using simulated data with 2% added Gaussian noise (measurement error). (a) Best sensor configuration with 9 sensors obtained for moderate measurement and modelling error; $U = 5.21$ corresponding to 91.32% of U_{\max} ; average strain error 1.67%; average input error 11.87%. (b) Arbitrarily selected sensor configuration with 9 sensors; $U = 3.88$ corresponding to 68% of U_{\max} ; average strain error 4.23%; average input error 16.21%.

Similar results are presented in Figure 16, corresponding to inflicted modelling errors instead of measurement errors. The modelling errors are introduced by simulating measurements from a FE model of the plate with all nodal masses perturbed independently by 10% (a zero-mean Gaussian

perturbation with standard deviation 0.1 is used) around their nominal values. The relative errors in the strain predictions using the optimal sensor configuration for moderate measurement and large modelling error corresponding to information gain of 93% of U_{\max} remain less than approximately 3% with an average relative error to be 1.14% over the plate surface, while the relative errors for the arbitrarily selected sensor configuration corresponding to lower information gain of 71% of U_{\max} is significantly higher with an average relative error of 5.6%. The average relative errors computed for the input predicted by AKF and simulated input are found to be 49.4% and 21.74% for the arbitrary and the optimal sensor configuration, respectively.

Figure 16: Relative errors in strain response predictions for white noise excitation using simulated data with 10% modelling error. (a) Best sensor configuration with 9 sensors obtained for moderate measurement and large modelling error; $U = 3.16$ corresponding to 93% of U_{\max} ; average strain error 1.14%; average input error 21.74%. (b) Arbitrarily selected sensor configurations with 9 sensors; $U = 2.41$ corresponding to 71% of U_{\max} ; average strain error 5.60%; average input error 49.4%.

The study is repeated for impulse excitation applied at location A. The impulse is simulated as a triangular excitation of maximum value of one and duration equal to $t_0 = T_8/5$, where T_8 is the modal period of the last contributing mode. For $t > t_0$ the triangular excitation is set to zero. The discretization time is $\Delta t = t_0/6$. The duration of the response to impulse excitation is selected to be approximately $T = -\log(0.1)/(\zeta_1\omega_1)$, where $\omega_1 = 2\pi f_1$ is the first modal frequency with f_1 is the value of the fundamental modal frequency in Hz given in Table 1. At the end of the duration T , the response is expected to fall off to approximately 10% of the maximum response values observed in the beginning of the excitation. Simulated data for the acceleration and strain response time histories over the plate surface are generated by adding in each time history a Gaussian noise of standard deviation equal to 2% of the acceleration and strain intensity.

Results for the effectiveness of the optimal and arbitrary sensor configurations involving 9 sensors are shown in Figures 17a and 17b, respectively. The average relative error over the plate surface is 25% for the arbitrary sensor configuration which should be compared to the average relative error of 13% for the optimal sensor configuration. The average relative errors computed between input time history predicted by AKF and the simulated input for the duration $0 - t_0$ sec are found to be 27% and 18% for the arbitrary and optimal sensor configuration (for $0 - t_0$ sec). The errors for the arbitrarily selected sensor configuration are found to be significantly higher than the ones for the optimal sensor configuration, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed optimal sensor placement methodology.

Figure 17: Relative errors in strain response predictions for impulse excitation using simulated data with 2% added Gaussian noise (measurement error). (a) Best sensor configuration with 9 sensors obtained for moderate measurement and modelling error; $U = 5.21$, 91.3% of U_{max} , average strain error 13%, average input error 18%. (b) Arbitrarily selected sensor configuration with 9 sensors; $U = 3.88$, 68% of U_{max} , average strain error 25%, average input error 27%.

5. Conclusions

A methodology is presented for optimizing the type and location of sensors in a structure for reliable response and input reconstruction (virtual sensing) using output-only vibration measurements. AKF is used for input-state estimation and virtual sensing. The utility function to be optimized is defined as the information gained from the data during the measurement update step of the AKF, quantified as the KL-div between the prior and the posterior PDF of the response QoI. Due to the linearity of the dynamic system and the Gaussian nature of the input and response predictions, the utility is formulated in terms of the corresponding variances of the prediction errors of the input and/or response QoI using steady-state solutions. Then, the utility is extended to account for uncertainties in structural model parameters, as well as measurement and modelling error parameters.

Two types of optimization methods, a heuristic algorithm and a GA algorithm, are used to estimate the optimal and worst sensor configurations as a function of the number of sensors. For the heuristic algorithm, various versions of the SSP algorithm are introduced and tested for computational efficiency and accuracy. Comparisons between different optimization approaches are made, from which the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The FSSP algorithm is by far the computationally most efficient one but may suffer from accuracy problems.
- For a sufficiently large number of sensors, the BSSP algorithm is the most accurate one, but it requires orders of magnitude higher computational cost than FSSP or GA.
- A new modified M-BSSP heuristic algorithm is also proposed to drastically reduce the computational burden to levels that are orders of magnitude less than the GA algorithm, while maintaining the accuracy of the original BSSP algorithm.

- GA provides nearly optimal solutions. However, for a sufficiently large number of sensors, the outcome is less accurate than the ones estimated by BSSP or M-BSSP.
- The combined estimate of heuristic FSSP, M-BSSP, and GA algorithms can be used to attain a suitable sensor configuration.

The proposed methodology was demonstrated by designing the optimal location of strain and/or acceleration sensors over the surface of a plate structure subjected to a single excitation at a known location. A thorough investigation of the effect of plant/process, measurement, modelling and prediction errors, as well as the intensity of the excitation was conducted, considering the uncertainties in these errors on the optimal type and location of sensors and on the variation of the highest and lowest information gain as a function of the number of sensors. It is demonstrated that an increase in measurement and modelling errors decreases the information gain.

The proposed framework can fuse a mixed-type of acceleration and strain sensors which can be significantly more informative than sensor configurations involving only acceleration sensors. It also provides optimal sensor configurations that are robust to uncertainties in model parameters as well as in modelling, prediction and measurement errors. Such uncertainties are not known in the initial optimal experimental design phase and thus are postulated using prior distributions. The robust designs over wide uncertainty bounds of errors leads to optimal sensor placement designs that are closer to the ones obtained for high measurement and modelling/prediction errors. Finally, the effectiveness of the optimal designs was validated against sub-optimal ones by comparing errors in the predictions between the AKF method and simulated measurements contaminated by noise or model errors. Although a simple plate structure with specific boundary conditions has been chosen to illustrate the capabilities of the methodology, one can use the methodology to explore its capabilities to alternative boundary conditions for the plate as well as apply it to more complicated structures.

The proposed information-theoretic OSP framework is general and can handle linear and non-linear systems. However, the use of AKF in this work restricts its applicability to linear structural systems. Future work will focus on expanding the framework to integrate alternative Bayesian filtering techniques for input-state estimation for linear systems, as well as extend the use of the framework to handle Bayesian filtering techniques for input-state-parameter estimation and nonlinear structural systems.

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